

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EXTENDING THE UNDERSTANDING OF HEALTH MECHANISMS: INVERSE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN WORSENING OF CELLS' METABOLISM AND ARTERIAL PRESSURE

Grygoryan R.

PhD, Dr. of Biol. Sciences, Prof., Head of department "Human systems modeling", Cybernetics center of National Academy of Sciences, Institute of software systems, Kyiv, Ukraine

Abstract

Human health parameters are currently conventionally based on statistics for healthy and diseased populations. Applying such parameters to patients, medics meet with problems of individual variations and dynamics. Concepts explaining the origin of the unstable parametric landscape are absent. An augmented by thought experiments critical analysis of empirical data led to an adequate view of multi-scale physiological mechanisms permanently trying to minimize destructions in cells. Cytoplasm-nucleus interaction is the basis for adapting current catabolic-anabolic rates. Mitochondria using pyruvate and oxygen are the main providers of biochemical energy (ATP molecules). Normally, within limited ranges of ATP usage rate, multiple intracellular mechanisms dynamically adapt the proper rate of ATP synthesis. It is argued that in human organism, there exist signal pathways and multi-scale mechanisms enhancing the energy balance range in cells. Under certain organism-scale conditions, a compensatory elevation of arterial pressure minimizes cell metabolism deterioration caused by mitochondrial inefficiency or cytoplasm contamination.

Keywords: mitochondria, cardiovascular system, kidney, integrative physiology, neurohormonal control, hypertension.

1. Introduction

The general view on cardiovascular physiology [1-3] combines principles of circulation mechanics (CM) [4] with multiple hemodynamic effects of nervous-hormonal mechanisms revealed experimentally [5-6]. This approach mainly explaining central and regional hemodynamics ignores an important uncertainty – which mechanisms are responsible for long-term parameters of the cardiovascular system (CVS). Such ignorance had given rise to two fundamental physiological-medical problems: i) there is still no theoretical argumentation for the individually optimal arterial pressure (OAP); ii) there is no understanding of the physiological mechanisms throughout life altering OAP. In particular, mechanisms of essential (primary) arterial hypertension (EAH) that accounts for more than 90% of all hypertensive patients [7] have not yet been understood.

CM formally describes dependencies between cardiovascular parameters (total blood volume, heart rate and contractility, vascular compliances, and resistances) on the one hand, and blood variables (pressures, volumes, and flows) on the other hand [4]. Currently, CM is the theoretical basis for clinical assessments of the human CVS including procedures aimed to correct (normalize) the shifted states of hemodynamic characteristics [6,8]. In particular, the arterial hypertension (AH) is considered to be one of the shifted states of CVS [9], thus it seems well argued that AH's cure aims to lower the elevated arterial pressure (EAP) at the levels of so-called normal arterial pressure (NAP). However, NAP is a conventional but not a theoretically argued notion. CM does not explain the level of OAP or its providers. Moreover, there is no concept capable to explain mechanisms setting and governing long-term characteristics of CVS. The revealed neural and hormonal mechanisms, influencing blood circulation, only alter the current values of arterial pressure

and cardiac output via modulating heart contractility and rate, regional vascular parameters [10]. These controllers (regulators) are not responsible for structural adaptive rearrangements of myocardium or body vasculature. At the same time, a lot of data evidently show structural and functional shifts in professional sportsmen's CVS. Another type of data concerns EAH covering more than 90% of all hypertensive patients [8], but the exact underlying mechanisms remain ambiguous [11]. Despite multiple potential ways for a developing of EAH, till now none concept of EAH's origin is commonly accepted. In contrast, the suggestion that clinical cases of AH are the late stages of pathological transformations of physiological mechanisms responsible for EAH is almost commonly accepted both by physiologists and by medics.

To clarify these uncertainties, special systems analysis is required. The biggest medical question of the analysis is whether the cure strategy of EAP really does help the organism. But this question cannot be correctly answered without clarifying another problem: whether there are unknown yet fundamental mechanisms permanently governing the development of CVS during life span? Observation data accumulated during decades of years give a reason to assume that there must be special adapters of the CVS to altering needs of cells. The CVS is a participant of systems functionally integrated in super-systems that provide optimal-like metabolism of cells despite casual alterations of physicochemical parameters of local internal environment [11]. Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that the other participant organs and systems are also under that hypothetical yet mechanisms providing the permanent rearrangements. However, the known empiric research of CVS had been mainly constructed to investigate partial mechanisms that control acute or long-term parameters

of CVS in specific situations. There is no concept explaining of mechanisms that determine (set and govern) primary parameters of CVS.

The goal of this article is to theoretically argue a novel view on the functioning of CVS by conditioning its dynamics with the dynamics of states of organs and systems that coevolved to provide optimal-like metabolism of most cells.

The characteristic feature of the non-standard article is that proves are based on combination of the critical analysis of empirics with thought experiments.

2. Prerequisites to rethink mechanisms of arterial pressure control

In recent years, mitochondrial dysfunction has been reported as an important contributor to the pathogenesis of hypertension-related renal, cardiac, and vascular disease [12-16].

The predominant knowledge about mechanisms governing an organism's existence in unstable environments is provided by empirics. However, empiricism has its principal limits – it is impossible to simultaneously control the enormous number of cellular dynamic characteristics for every cell of the intact human organism containing about 50 trillion cells. Every response of the entire organism or even its structural-functional components to external or/and internal given dynamics may be very complex. Experimental models of empirical physiology try to reduce the complexity in ways that allow quantitative evaluation of investments of certain mechanisms in the general response.

The problem of complexity is common in most natural sciences. As physics has been intensively developed and quantified earlier than physiology, it is useful to consider approaches proposed by physicists. Historically, behaviors of gases, liquids, and solids were the problems physics first tried to explain using mathematics. Two main alternative approaches were developed. The first alternative was the creation of mathematical physics based on statistics and probabilities and operating with populations of elementary components. The main lack of these methods is that they cannot accurately describe the behavior of an element of the population. To eliminate this shortcoming, physicists successfully use the second alternative – thought experiments. Some of them became a basis for mathematical models and computer simulators, especially in modern cosmology and quantum physics. Although most of these experiments are almost impossible to provide in the real world, the logical conclusions obtained often indicate to experimenters what should be avoided altogether and where good experimental results can be obtained. This method can also be used to reveal fundamental physiological patterns and mechanisms inaccessible in the frame of modern empirics.

Multicellular organisms had been formed using single-celled ancestors that already had accumulated conservative mechanisms providing organism survival within a certain range of local physical-chemical destructive alterations. It is reasonable to assume that these fundamental mechanisms function in human cells too. If so, within certain local physical-chemical conditions, every specialized cell provides its basic functions (metabolism, cell cycle, and conservative responses to

external influences). During long evolution, specific organs and their functional systems were saved because they provided additional chances for organism survival. If the logic is true, our organism possesses a functional super-system (FSS) that enhances the potential of cells to survive in the background of destructive trends [11]. Continuing the logic one can conclude that FSS will minimize the time interval dangerous for the cell life. The way to this goal includes providing optimal material incomes and metabolic waste removal. Namely, components of FSS (digestive system, external respiratory system, CVS, skin, kidneys, as well as their humoral and nervous controllers) will operatively react to deterioration of cell metabolism and try to provide currently optimal-like multiparametric landscape for minimizing intracellular destructions for a maximal number of cells. In particular, this understanding of FSS brought us to the paradigm of “floating” arterial pressure [9] and cells' contribution to arterial pressure [10]. The concept of FSS became a platform for a novel view of integrative physiology [11]. These conceptual shifts suggest that the cell's basic functions should be at the center of the physiological thought experiment. Potentially, every logical experiment compatible with cell life is allowed. Since the life-support functions are supported by almost every specialized cell, therefore every thought experiment is suitable if it concerns cellular basic functions and includes two phases: 1) the mechanisms analyzed initially deteriorate the life-support; 2) via activating compensator mechanisms the cell's basic functions become recovered. In the thought experiment, energy and material support for cell metabolism can be two main aspects. Hence, reasonable is in the first thought experiment analyze the cell energy balance (CEB) under elevation or lowering of ATP consumption rate, while the second thought experiment concerns deterioration of cell metabolism rate.

3. The thought experiment #1: violations of cell energy balance

The energy released during the breakdown of ATP molecules provides every biological work. CEB is a widely used physiological notion but not formalized duly. Therefore, a formal analysis of this notion and factors and circumstances violating CEB is necessary. In real organism, CEB is an ideal but transitory state possible on different energy levels of every specialized cell.

A healthy cell has a certain number of ATP molecules previously synthesized either in the cytoplasm (via anaerobe glycolysis of carbohydrates) or in mitochondria (by oxidative phosphorylation of pyruvate – another product of anaerobe glycolysis). Mitochondria producing about 90% of cell ATP need several renewable chemicals (inorganic phosphor, and *NADH*) and inflows of two consumables – oxygen and pyruvate. Including also the minor number of ATP provided via anaerobe glycolysis, CEB is possible until the income of consumables compensates for their loss.

Let us assume that at the time moment $t = 0$, the cell is in a CEB state characterized by an energy state $E(t) = E_0$. For every time interval of τ , the current

energy state is: $E(\tau) = E_0 + \int_0^{\tau} (v_s(t) - v_c(t)) dt$.

Here $v_s(t)$ and $v_c(t)$ represent the rates of ATP synthesis and consumption respectively. Under $v_s(t) = v_c(t)$, $E(\tau) = E_0$. Usually, $v_s(t) > v_c(t)$ and $E(\tau) \geq E_0$. At the same time, under decreasing cell loads, special situations of $E(\tau) < E_0$ also can appear. Under extreme states of $E(\tau) < 0$, specific states of energy lack appear. This energy status may appear in two scenarios: 1) when additional influences compel the cell to increase current $v_c(t)$ on some $\Delta v_c(\tau)$; 2) when the cell is compelled to decrease the rate of ATP synthesis $v_s(t)$ on some $\Delta v_s(\tau)$. Despite the resulting effect of these scenarios is formally the same ($\Delta E(\tau)$), physiological events provided by the cell under energy deficit (ED) are different.

3.1. Intracellular compensators of ED

Under ED, some of the life processes requiring ATP will be inhibited or broken in their interim stages. If ED lasts further, intermediate metabolic agents gradually accumulating in the cell deteriorate the quality of the cytoplasm. So, the cell is immersed in stagnation. If the stagnated cell is a part of a multicellular organ, its output function stagnates too. An organ's functional deterioration depends on the amount of stagnated cells. The logic used here schematically indicates the causal relationship between cell energy lack and macroscopic physiological function. Reasonable is to suggest that the cell is evolutionarily acquired by mechanisms coping (in some limits) with the energy lack. Indeed, some intracellular mechanisms more or less successfully combating the energy lack and recovering the metabolism are already known. Without going into details of different types of cells, we can schematically analyze the main intracellular compensator events.

3.1.1. Biochemical negative feedbacks

In general, biochemical negative feedbacks exist based on the concentration ratios of ADP/ATP and AMP/ATP. The decrease of $E(\tau)$ accelerates $v_s(\tau)$ via increase of cytoplasmic concentration of ADP. Effects of the same direction occur under a decrease of ADP: the velocity of AMP synthesis, using mitochondrial concentrations of pyruvate and oxygen, elevates. These two biochemical negative feedbacks are the most fast-acting autonomous mechanisms trying to balance $v_s(\tau)$ with $v_c(\tau)$. However, the efficiency of this mechanism decreases with increasing of $\Delta v_c(\tau)$. Thus let us analyze other regulators too.

Theoretically $v_s(\tau)$ is a function of the following variables:

$S_s(t)$ – characterizes the summary surface of internal membranes of cell mitochondria; $C_{py}(t)$ – represents the pyruvate concentration; $C_{O_2}(t)$ – represents the oxygen concentration; $C_{pi}(t)$ – represents the concentration of inorganic phosphor;

$C_N(t)$ – represents the concentration of *NADH*

Within short-time intervals of τ , $S_s(t) \approx const$.

$C_{py}(t)$ depends on $v_s(t)$ and pyruvate incomes depending on the cytoplasmic concentration of glucose and other carbohydrates. Oxygen incomes, depending on $P_aO_2(t)$ and local blood flow, elevate $C_{O_2}(t)$ while the increase of $v_s(t)$ decreases $C_{O_2}(t)$. Elevations of the gradient between the mean pressures in aortic arch (MAP) and central vena (CVP) increase the cardiac output (CO), while increases in the total ($R(t)$) decrease CO. Regional vascular resistances ($r(t)$) distribute CO to organs. Farther localization of flows depends on nuances of microvasculature nets. At the microscopic scale of a cell colony, each cell takes nutrients using their concentration gradients between the liquid intercellular environment and cell cytoplasm.

This formalization suggests that for every $S_s(t) \approx const$, under certain values of involved characteristics, the current value of $v_s(t)$ is a part of its theoretical maximum ($V_s(t)$). So, multiple mechanisms capable of altering blood flow can modulate the cell energy status. In other words, the intracellular rearrangements for elevation of $v_s(t)$ have at least a hemodynamic extracellular enhancer. It is effective until the arterial blood contains the required concentrations of carbohydrates and oxygen. Under their lack, other ways must be activated. These additional potential enhancers are considered below.

3.1.2. Ways for compensating the oxygen lack

It is well-known that normally an essential amount of erythrocytes is deposited in spleen and liver. Their mobilization into the active circulation helps to provide the organs actually having a higher metabolism. So, under energy scarce caused by oxygen lack reflector constrictions of spleen and liver can add to circulation a certain number of oxygen carriers – erythrocytes. An increase of the velocity of lung ventilation ($v_L(t)$) is another independent mechanism potentially capable of fast elevating $C_{O_2}(t)$. At last, an increase of erythropoiesis is the third though slow elevator of $C_{O_2}(t)$. Activators of this mechanism known as hypoxia inducible factors (HIF's) are already revealed [17].

It is well-known that under physiological norm an essential amount of erythrocytes is deposited in the spleen and liver. Therefore, organs sharply increasing their metabolism can be provided additional oxygen through portions of erythrocytes mobilized from their

depots. So, under energy scarcity caused by oxygen lack reflector constrictions of the spleen and liver can add to circulation a certain number of oxygen carriers – erythrocytes.

An increase in the velocity of lung ventilation ($v_L(t)$) is another independent mechanism capable of fast elevating $C_{O_2}(t)$. Reflector mechanisms based on chemoreceptors sensing blood pH , $PaCO_2$, and PaO_2 and controlling $C_{O_2}(t)$ are well-known. Perhaps it is worth to stress here that both peripheral and central chemoreflexes also are altering MAP [1,2].

At last, an increase of erythropoiesis is the third though slow elevator of $C_{O_2}(t)$. Activators of this mechanism known as hypoxia-inducible factors (HIFs) are already revealed [17,18]. The role of HIFs is essential under chronic local or regional ED caused by oxygen lack.

3.1.3. Ways for compensating the glucose lack

The lack of carbohydrates finally transforming into glucose and pyruvate is an independent originator of ATP lack. Even in the background of the functionality of mitochondria and a sufficient amount of oxygen, the lack of glucose slows the metabolism down. Therefore, a search for mechanisms capable of compensating or mitigating this negative biological effect is argued. The empirical physiology mainly accentuated problems associated with diabetes and mechanisms of pancreas-liver interactions regulating blood concentrations of glucose, insulin, glycogen, and glucagon [19]. Despite investigations showing glucagon's influence on CO [20], the energetic aspect of this factor remains unclear yet.

At the cell scale, glucose lack firstly decreases the concentration of AMP. Multiple investigations revealed cell-scale and organism-scale compensatory responses to this situation. The main pathways are associated with AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) [21]. When activated by nutrient deficiency, AMPK stimulates glucose uptake and lipid oxidation to produce energy, while shutting down energy-consuming processes, including glucose and lipid production, to restore energy balance. AMPK acts as a sensor of internal adenosine phosphate levels and inhibits energy consumption pathways, and supports energy glycolysis and glycogenolysis [22]. Exercise leads to the activation of AMPK in skeletal muscle, in abdominal adipose tissue, liver, and other organs [23]. In addition to its normal role as an intracellular energy switch or fuel sensor, new research has shown that AMPK is a redox sensor and modulator that plays a key role in maintaining cardiovascular processes and inhibiting disease progression. In response to stressors that increase AMP levels in cells of the arterial wall, AMPK lowers blood pressure, but the effect of hyperlipidemia on this response has not been studied. Relatives of AMPK are found in essentially all eukaryotes, and it may have evolved to allow the host cell to monitor the output of the newly acquired mitochondria and step their ATP production up or down according to the demand [23].

3.1.4. Ways for increasing local (regional) hemodynamics without elevation of MAP

Elevation of perfusion pressure is not the exclusive way to increase local or regional hemodynamics. Under sufficient concentration of blood nutrients, vasodilation is among first line ways effectively minimizing up to middle severity acute lack of cell incomes. This opportunity is well-known in skeletal muscles, internal organs, and skin. Multiple endogenous vasodilator agents, increasing blood flow into tissues that need oxygen, glucose, lipids, and other nutrients, are known (adenosine, epinephrine, nitric oxide, prostaglandin, histamine, natriuretic peptides, hypoxia-inducible factors Hif1 α , Hif1 β , and others). However, under a big number of ED-cells, because of TPR's, and MAP's lowering, the efficiency of the vasodilation decreases. Under continuous regional ED, in addition to vasodilation, a neogenesis of microvasculature is activated. Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is a highly specific mitogen and inducer of angiogenesis and lymphangiogenesis. HIFs regulate the metabolic and angiogenic activity in endothelial cells under both normal and hypoxic conditions and in diseases that are associated with cardiovascular complications [24]. Multiple publications reported that vascular endothelial growth factor inhibitors lead to hypertension [25].

3.1.4.1. Mitochondrial responses to long-term ED

Under relatively short-time alterations of energy demands in cells, mitochondria mainly use the fusion-fission mechanism [26,27]. In cell types with mostly uneven oxygen distribution, mitochondria use their motility to reach local areas with a higher oxygen concentration. This strategy is effective in neurons possessing long dendrites and axons. If the total effect provided by these mechanisms, and feed-back mechanisms based on concentrations of ADP/ATP is not able to recover CEB, additional mechanisms become activated. Theoretically, both the hypertrophy and proliferation of existing mitochondria result in growth of $S_s(t)$. These biosynthetic rearrangements require a proper continuous increase of nutrients inflow. To provide this goal, a complex mechanism combining control of expression in DNA's specific sites with activation of multicellular mechanisms responsible for incomes of source materials to the local surrounding area of ED-cells, will exist. The necessity of such a hypothetic mechanism was argued in [10]. The functionality of this hypothesis had been tested with specially created quantitative mathematical models [28]. Perhaps, the fact that between levels of MAP and the activity of other participants of FSS is an inverse relationship was the most valuable simulation result [29,30]. So, MAP elevates in cases only when other participants of FSS are not capable of providing the required structural enlargement of total $S_s(t)$ of cell mitochondria.

4. Special case: heart function under hypoglycemia

Mitochondria play a pivotal role in the energy providing of cardiac myocytes and the due values of CO [3]. At first glance, the assertion that a heart under low glucose can increase CO and MAP seems illogical. Indeed, what is the energy source? However, at least two empirically well-provided facts illustrate such an

effect. Usually, about 70% of ATP molecules synthesized in cardiomyocytes use fatty acids. Besides, in pancreas beta cells, the low blood glucose activates a glucagon release. The glucagon generally elevates the blood glucose levels by promoting gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis. Glucagon has potent positive inotropic and chronotropic effects on the heart. In the myocardium, glucagon dilates arterioles and increases the local blood flow [1]. Therefore, despite scarce blood glucose, heart functionality can be provided at levels for elevating CO and MAP.

5. The thought experiment #2: deterioration of cell metabolism because of cytoplasmic contamination

Intracellular biochemical transformations are optimal only in certain ranges of temperature and ionic composition of the cytoplasm. The ranges specific to different cell types are also associated with the phases of the cell cycle. Since blood circulation contributes to the formation of the physicochemical parameters of the cytoplasm, it is reasonable to believe that the mechanisms of maintaining temperature homeostasis, water-electric, and acid-base balances are somehow associated with the functioning of the CVS. Therefore, it is reasonable to come up with such thought experiments in which the adaptive changes of blood pressure to restore optimal cytoplasm should develop.

First, let's consider a situation where the removal of unnecessary metabolic waste is lower than the rate of their accumulation. Originators of such situations can be a) a deterioration of lymphatic flow; b) a decrease in venous outflow; c) inadequacy of the purifier organs (kidneys, skin, and lungs) efficiency to the existent rate of deterioration in the quality of the cytoplasm.

Perhaps it is necessary to make an additional reservation here. The deterioration of the cytoplasm quality in one cell or a relatively small number of cells (up to millions) cannot significantly affect the organism-scale function of the organ. Therefore, these cases are unlikely to cause significant (observable) changes in systemic blood pressure levels. Only a simultaneous deterioration in the quality of the cytoplasm of tens of millions, most likely billions of cells, will lead to the observed shifts in the parameters of the central circulation. Additional nuances the reader should pay attention to are analyzed in section "discussion".

Renal disfunction is the most known example to explain mechanisms elevating MAP as a way to overcome blood and cytoplasm contaminations by metabolic wastes. Although the pathogenesis of hypertension is not yet fully understood, the disruption of the renin-angiotensin system (RAS), consisting of the systemic and brain RAS, has been recognized as one of the primary reasons for several types of hypertension [31,32].

In the body, separation of water and its dissolved substances is important for understanding the physiology of spaces with body fluids. The modern view of fluid circulation in the body is an active double circulation of extracellular fluid that allows solutes to move into and out of intracellular fluid. Various factors that

determine fluid flow across cell membranes and microvascular permeability barriers, including hydrostatic pressure differences and solute concentration gradients, concern CVS. Total body water and body sodium are regulated. Changes in extracellular fluid osmolality, in potassium and sodium balance depend on sufficient magnesium availability. $[Na^+]$ concentrations in body fluids are maintained at 135–145 mM and are generally conservative. Severe hyper- or hypotonicity causes irreversible organ damage and lethal neurological injury. To achieve Na homeostasis, the brain constantly monitors the $[Na^+]$ content of body fluids and controls water/salt intake and water/salt excretion by the kidneys. These physiological functions are primarily regulated based on information from $[Na^+]$ and related circulating hormones such as angiotensin II, aldosterone, and vasopressin [33].

6. Discussion

Ideas about mechanisms that regulate the state of CVS have undergone a certain evolution. For a long time, the concept of prevailing nervous regulation of the pumping function of the heart and the tone of regional vessels dominated. In particular, arterial baroreceptor reflexes (ABR) are supposed to be the main mechanism that minimizes perturbations of the mean arterial pressure (MAP) despite regular violations of arterial pressure in each cardiac cycle. In addition, MAP is under regulator influences of chemoreflexes (CHR): at least, alterations of blood pH, $PaCO_2$, and PaO_2 activate peripheral chemoreceptors located in specific bulbs of the aortic arch and carotid sinuses. Both CVS and lung ventilation are under CHR. Central (cRAS) [31] and local (IRAS) renin-angiotensin systems are considered the main humoral mechanism capable of essential elevation of MAP [32].

The long-term trends of MAP were and remain in the focus of clinicians too. In order to clarify whether MAP's shifts like chronic hypertension or hypotension have a compensatory or pathologic origin, clinicians need an adequate concept explaining the mechanisms of these shifts. But special investigations have shown that ABR and CHR are not responsible for the long-term level of MAP [5]. Therefore, by the mid-1960s, the special concept of neurohumoral regulation of MAP came to the fore [1]. The key point of the concept is the involvement of renal mechanisms ensuring blood water-electrolytic homeostasis. Further exploring these main concepts over time revealed nuances supporting the thought that the overall control of CVS is likely tricky. Currently, despite the intensive research on multiple aspects of arterial hypertension (AH), neither physiology of CVS nor the origin of its pathology is completely understood. At the same time, the current fight against secondary AH is aimed at reducing the influences of CNS and local humoral mechanisms on MAP's three main determinants (total blood volume, heart pumping function, systemic vascular compliance, and resistance). Clarifying of real roles of these three characteristics of CVS could help a computer model (CM), that describes the functions of mechanisms regulating CVS, and that is properly realized as special software (SS).

Physiologists have long believed that CVS is a self-controlled system. If so, CVS would possess by its autonomously acting control mechanisms. Despite intuitively it was clear that the cardiac output (CO) is CVS's output function in which organism, its cells as end-users need, almost every hemodynamic regulator is based on afferent impulse patterns provided by mechanoreceptors. Phenomena causally associated with intravascular receptors reacting to alterations of mechanical shear of fluid flow have been rarely described and are still marginal yet [1,4]. Therefore, special theories integrating the heart output with arterial pressure through total peripheral resistance are still in the mainstream of current cardiovascular physiology [1].

In this critical analysis, the author stresses that every view on CVS as if it is an autonomously functioning system with its goals and effector mechanisms is fundamentally incorrect. The CVS is only a functional component of a more complex functional systems that have been long co-evolved and saved because they together solve the fundamental problem of every cell, namely, create optimal-like cytoplasm environment as the necessary condition for minimizing cellular damages. From this indisputable point of view, the dominant concepts concerning circulation should be essentially extended. In the focus of biological events, the most argued concept will locate basic transformations and their regulators, that initially appeared in an ancestor cell, then, even being long evolved in form of animals' specialized cells, continue to provide non-specific functions of cell life support. Every additional mechanism born during further evolution can be saved in case only if the novel combination at least did not work against Darwinian evolution.

Another widespread belief among cardiologists is that the main cause of increased blood pressure is atherosclerotic plaques. There is truth in this, but not all. This reason does not reveal the entire chain of mechanisms, the sequential deployment of which gives rise to urgent or sustained hypertension. Only computer modeling that examined hemodynamics with cardiovascular regulation mechanisms turned off or on allowed us to understand the full cause-and-effect relationship [28]. Indeed, in the model that described the general regulation of the cardiovascular system, imitation of an increase in total peripheral vascular resistance led to the development of a complex reaction: against the background of preserved CO, MAP increased. At the same time, there was an increase in both the pumping function of the heart (inotropism and HR) and the tone of the veins. It was the latter circumstance that contributed to the increase in central venous pressure. If the same increase in total peripheral vascular resistance was simulated, but with the regulatory circuits turned off, then the increase in MAP was both slightly less and occurred with a simultaneous decrease in CO. Analysis of these simulations leads to a clear conclusion: the body tries to compensate for the drop in blood flow in all possible ways. Moreover, it is the lack of carbohydrates and oxygen that initiates the activation of compensatory mechanisms that can provide cells with energy. An additional argument in favor of this point of view is the

body's response with a hypertensive crisis to the deterioration of the metabolism of any large (important for the whole organism) organ. It is well known that hypertensive crises develop not only in response to disorders of the excretory function of the kidneys, but also under various etiologies of ischemia of almost any organ (brain, liver, regional skeletal muscles, endocrine glands).

To clarify additional mechanisms altering the activity of CVS physiologists have to answer what parameters of circulation are subject to these mechanisms? Initially, the required mechanisms were considered to be reflector mechanisms, the receptors of which are concentrated in different parts of the heart and arterial bed. However, multiple studies have shown that reflex mechanisms predominantly neutralize sharp fluctuations in blood pressure (for example, those that occur during each cardiac cycle) but have almost no relation to the long-term level of mean arterial pressure. Arterial hypertension is often associated with impaired renal function. The data have put forward the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone hormonal system as a new candidate regulatory mechanism. It would seem that this view received additional support from the results of studies that discovered renin with deteriorations in the metabolism of the heart, liver, lungs, and brain. Current views on CVS regulators are based on combinations of neurohormonal mechanisms.

6.1. Some thoughts about the structural-functional element

The so-called structural-functional element (SFE) of every multicellular organism must be clarified, including the human body. The clarification is required because most biologists commonly suggest the specialized cell is SFE. This suggestion leads to a misunderstanding of the true processes of adaptation of cells and multicellular formations, including organs and the whole organism, to the challenges of the living environment. Only after the fact that in every multicellular organism, colonies are the evolutionarily acquired way for the existence of specialized cells was realized, fundamental mechanisms of the individual adaptation to internal/external environmental challenges were revealed [34,35].

During life span, natural consequence of serial mitoses of each type of specialized cell is a cell colony. Certainly, colonies of different cell types may essentially differ in their size. Much more significant is here that the number of sister cells normally is dynamic even in the frame of one of the same colony. Variations of the colony size can be sporadic or regular depending on multiple internal and external actors. Below the attention is mainly focused on circumstances capable of masking important biological effects associated with the paper's subject.

Within the same colony, different generation sister cells are not identical clones but have small internal differences. Their origin is conditioned both by the initial uneven division of certain molecules and organelles like mitochondria during mitosis and by the unique spatial-temporal physicochemical conditions of the maturation of each daughter cell. Only at first glance, such heterogeneities in a cell colony are devoid of biological

consequences. A more in-depth analysis showed that fluctuations in the functional activity of a single-organ or multi-organ functional system go back precisely to cellular anisotropies. A good sample is the heart myocardium providing nonlinear contractility-relaxation curves during a single cardiac cycle. But rare cardiologists associate the graph forms of the myocardium contractility dynamics or the dynamics of ventricular pressure (consequently, aortic arch and arterial pressures) with the statistical distribution of cardiomyocytes' amount possessing given values of their sensitivity threshold or saturation level.

A novel theoretical view on the integrative functioning of specialized cells being structural-functional components of complex organs was consequentially developed [10,34]. The fundamental hypothesis suggests that evolutionary success came to multicellular communities (plants, and animals) that used colonies of specialized dynamic cells as structural-functional units for creating organs and their functional systems. The utility of such systems is in providing two functions: 1) creation of optimal chemistry of cytoplasm; and 2) material flows necessary for maximizing the rate of metabolism. As environmental instability may destroy the optimality, special regulators based on negative feedback later have been occurred and saved. These multicellular feedbacks, added to intracellular feedback mechanisms using alterations of the expression in certain groups of genes, enhance their compensatory effects through adequate material inflows and outflows. Namely, this understanding of an organism's physiology explains practically every fact anywhere observed and published.

Generalizing the effects caused by heterogeneities of common-type cells, it is worth noting that internal ultrastructural differences determine the asynchronous responses of colony cells to the applied common stimulus. That is why the dynamics of the development of the colony function occur practically smoothly, but not stepwise. The phase of restoration of the colony's reactivity has the same inertial appearance. Thus, it is precisely because of the presence of fundamental biophysical and biochemical inhomogeneities of sister cells in a colony that the graph of the unfolding of its integral response to an incoming stimulus always looks nonlinear.

Additional long-term dynamic effects of the colony response are due to the internal mechanisms of cell adaptation: ultra-structural rearrangements minimize chronic molecular destruction [34,35]. Since a typical organ consists of multiple colonies functionally integrated in a certain way, the dynamics of the organ's functioning include all the effects associated with the specified nuances of its morpho-functional organization.

There exist mechanisms altering (increasing or decreasing) $S_s(t)$. As we are interested in understanding mechanisms compensating the energy lack, it reasonable is at first to consider mechanisms increasing $S_s(t)$

Fusion of mitochondrial units is the first, most rapid but relatively less powered grower of $S_s(t)$. Proliferation of the mitochondrial units is the second, inertial but much more powerful increaser of $S_s(t)$. Namely, this mechanism can be activated by chemicals accumulated in cytoplasm under energy scarcity and penetrate the nucleus. The general vision of the role playing by such mediator agents in the control of $E(\tau)$ is in altering of current expression of genes in certain DNA sites. So, the simulation of the expression in genes, providing mitochondrial proliferation, will lead to essential but slow elevation of $S_s(t)$. Mitochondrial motility is also known to play certain role in altering of $v_s(t)$ through changes of $S_s(t)$ but this specific option is essential mainly in big cells like neurons under uneven distribution of oxygen in soma and axons.

The key statement of the new understanding is that the CVS is only a part of a multi-scale and multi-organ functional super-system (FSS) evolutionarily completed to provide cells metabolism under casual dynamics of both catabolic and anabolic biochemical events. This view highlights the relativity of investments that each component of FSS actually can provide. Factors and circumstances moderating the roles of every component (in particular, CVS) in the functioning of FSS are described and discussed. Often modulations are associated with extracellular factors causing an imbalance of ATP synthesis and consumption rates. Autonomic self-scale chemical negative feedbacks, activating/deactivating DNA's particular sites to balance biosynthetic contours and balance rates of ATP synthesis with the imposed rates of energy consumption, represent the first "defense line". Another genetic mechanism starts a cascade of transformations eventually enlarging mitochondrial area and efficiency. In cases of its inefficiency, the second "defense line" becomes activated. Initiators of this defense are intermitted low-weight agents of impaired metabolism. Their accumulation in body fluids activates local vasodilatation increasing oxygen and nutrients' income to the impaired cells. In case of further inefficiency, some of these agents reach the target cells that belong to organs involved in the material providing of cell metabolism. This third "defense line" accelerates cytoplasm purification and provides a due rate of cell metabolism. In case of chronic local or organ-scale metabolic impairment, the mechanism of cell proliferation creates new microvasculature and/or organs' compensatory hypertrophy. As there exist a lot of optimal combinations of CVS's parameters and parameters of other components of FSS, it is not correct to insist on the existence of a single optimal (so-called normal) level of arterial pressure. This last conclusion concerns parameters of other components of FSS too.

Intracellular ultra-structural alterations including adaptive rearrangements are concerned either molecular destructions or up-buildings. So, every adaptation has its structural providers. From the other hand, every intracellular structural alteration not related to molecu-

lar destructions is provided by proper “building materials”. Their synthesis ratio is provided by proper expression of specific DNA sites. Empirically established the existence of various specialized cytoplasmic factors (CFs) which, penetrating into the cell nucleus and modulating the expression of specific DNA sites, regulate certain aspects of cellular metabolism. In the cell cycle, such interaction of CFs, genes, and metabolism underlies the autonomous adaptation (AA) of the cell to internal environmental challenges. AA includes changes in the number and size of a number of organelles (mitochondria, ribosomes, etc.). But the effectiveness of AA depends on the chemical composition of the cytoplasm. It is associated both with the flows and composition of incoming blood, and with the intensity of functioning of the excretory organs. Therefore, it can be assumed that there must be additional multicellular mechanisms (MMs), the activity of MMs does correlate with the frequency and severity of adaptive rearrangements of cell organelles. Moreover, there is reason to believe that the activity of MMs is regulated by low-molecular CFs, which, appearing in the cell during metabolic stagnation, are able to leave the cell and then enter the blood with the lymph flow. If such hypothetical enhancers of cellular adaptation really exist, then the body has a potential basis for multi-level optimization (material support) of the rates of organelles’ biosynthesis. By adding here some of the CFs capable of activating cell proliferation in the organ components of MMs, one can see a functionally integrated mechanism that can also regulate the sizes of macroscopic organs.

7. Conclusion

A huge number of the accumulated data concerning genetic–biochemical intracellular dynamics, orchestrated alterations of subcellular organelles (especially mitochondria), cell metabolism, developmental, and aging physiology, as well as human normal and pathological integrative physiology hardly can be explained in the frames of dominant medical-biological concepts. A critical analysis was used to clarify complex mechanisms that evolve biophysical and biochemical parameters throughout life. The hypothesis that every organism has multi-scale functional mechanisms permanently creating an optimal-like cytoplasm environment and minimizing long-term imbalances potentially destroying the cell was argued employing thought experiments. Instabilities of most biological characteristics, including those used as health indicators, are caused by these multi-scale mechanisms that alter life flows to balance the rate of biosynthetic transformations with the inevitably forced rate of molecular destructions. Regardless of the causes of suppressed metabolism in a large number of cells, the genetic and biochemical mechanisms of the cell, and, if necessary, multicellular enhancers of intracellular protective mechanisms become activated until the anabolism-catabolism balance is restored in deteriorated cells. A rise in MAP is only one of the ways that contribute to an adequate increase in the rate of biosynthesis. Correct assessments of human health dynamics require data for determining essential violations of life variables representing the entire multidimensional parametric land-

scape. Real biometrics is not representative. Understanding this principal restriction can help doctors better imagine the dynamics of non-trivial pathologies and propose their effective cures.

Main conclusions: 1) every rate of cell metabolism must be provided with both energy and substrates; 2) blood flows provided by pressure gradients play an assistant role in transporting of nutrients and oxygen into the cell, and in the removal of unnecessary metabolites from it; 3) mitochondria synthesize most of the ATP molecules; 4) at the proper concentrations of carbohydrates and oxygen, the total area of the internal membranes of cell mitochondria is the main determinant of the rate of ATP’s aerobic synthesis; 5) under critical lowering of cell metabolism, intermediate agents of two types become accumulating in the cell. Through negative feedback, agents of the first type influence gene expression and regulate ATP synthesis but to a limited extent. Agents of the second type leave the cell and, spreading with fluids, modulate the activity of a functional super-system (FSS) to provide the due metabolism. FSS includes systems of digestion, external respiration, the removal of metabolic wastes, as well as the CVS; 6) the ideal integral effect of such modulation is in restoring the energy balance on the rate of ATP molecules consumption. Enhancing mitochondrial health is emerging as a feasible approach to treat hypertension. The increasing of mean arterial pressure is only one of the ways to provide the integral effect thus OAP’s elevation reversible depends on activities of other components of FSS. Structural rearrangements in affected cells are optimal when the proper production capacity of mitochondria is provided. Difficulties on this path lead to a relatively increase of compensator roles of other ways commonly optimizing the cellular metabolism; 7) problems associated with cytoplasm biochemical purification are another originators of OAP’s alterations.

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